

Comparison of Three Methods for Quadratic Potential Propagators

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In this note, we compare three methods for calculating a propagator for a problem with a potential of the form $b(t)x + d(t)x \, dx/dt$ ((1)) and constant mass. Later, we consider making the mass time dependent as well.

The first method is that of (1) for which the form $Q(t)\exp\{-i [R(t)XX + V(t)YY + Z(t)XY]\}$ is postulated for the propagator and inserted into the time-dependent Schrodinger equation. Coefficients of various powers of X and Y are collected and taken to be zero as X and Y may be varied independently. This yields a set of differential equations for Q(t), R(t), V(t) and Z(t).

A second method is outlined in (2) and computes the propagator for ((1)) directly using solutions of the classical Newton's second law (without integrating them). This gives a structural form for the propagator, for example R(t) is of the form $dB/dt / B$ where B(t) is a function depending linearly on a solution to Newton's second law. It should be noted that this method suggests that a potential term in a classical Lagrangian $b(t)x \, dx/dt$ may be rewritten as $d/dt [g(t)xx] - g_1(t)xx$. Thus, the potential is written as $.5c(t)xx$ with the d/dt piece dropped as it has no consequences on the classical solutions. (We find that this leads to different results from (1).)

The third method is that of the classical action (3) i.e. calculating the propagator as $Q(t)\exp(i S_c)$ where S_c is the classical action which depends on solutions of Newton's law which are inserted into the Lagrangian which is then integrated over time.

In particular, we wish to show how the classical action approach is directly linked to the other two methods. The three methods are identical if the mass is constant and the quadratic potential is of the form $.5c(t)xx$ with no $b(t)x \, dx/dt$ piece. For methods 2 and 3 which use classical Lagrangians, a $b(t)x \, dx/dt$ potential term may be written as: $d/dt (g(t)xx) - g_2(t)xx$ with the $d/dt [g(t)xx]$ being dropped from the Lagrangian as it does not affect the equations of motion. For the time-dependent Schrodinger equation, one only has the Schrodinger equation with the fixed potential which cannot be changed. Thus, it seems that in the case of a $b(t)x(-idW/dx)$ term, the propagator obtained by this method differs with that of (2) if the xx and $x \, dx/dt$ potentials are converted into a strictly xx potential. If both potential pieces are left, then the method of (3) is still linked to (1), but in a more complicated manner. For the case of a pure $.5c(t)xx$ potential in the Schrodinger equation, the coefficient of XX from method (1) is proportional to $dA/dt / A$, where A is a solution of Newton's second law.

Time-Dependent Schrodinger Equation Approach

The approach of (1) is to postulate the form $Q(t) \exp\{-i [R(t)XX + V(t)YY + Z(t)XY]\}$ ((2)) for the propagator and to insert it into the time-dependent Hamiltonian which operates on X and t. A real differential equation is obtained for R(t) and a pure imaginary one linking R(t) and Q(t). Equations for V(t) and Z(t) are also obtained. This approach is straightforward and only involves the solution of differential equations. Furthermore, it may be immediately applied to the case of

a time dependent mass. A possible drawback is that it does not link the propagator directly to classical solutions of Newton's law.

In particular (1) shows the following results for the Schrodinger equation:

$$-i \frac{dW}{dt} = a \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} + b(t)xx - i c(t) x \frac{d}{dx} W - i d(t) W \quad ((3))$$

(Note: we drop two terms from ((2)) that are included in (1) which are linear not quadratic in x or d/dx.) Inserting ((2)) into ((3)) and considering coefficients of XX (pure real part) yields:

$$dR/dt + b(t) + 2c(t)R + 4a RR = 0 \quad ((4))$$

The pure imaginary part yields a differential equation linking Q(t) and R(t) and one may also find linked differential equations for V(t) and Z(t). We do not focus on those in this note. See (1) for all differential equations.

In order to find R(t), one must solve ((4)). It yields a function of time which, according to the method used, shows no immediate link to classical physics.

Direct Green's Function Approach

In (2), the propagator is obtained from a direct Green's function approach which starts with the idea of solutions to Newton's second law. First, however, the Lagrangian:

$$L = .5m \frac{dx}{dt} \frac{dx}{dt} - a_1(t) x \frac{dx}{dt} + .5 a_2(t) xx + \text{plus linear terms which we drop} \quad ((5))$$

is rewritten as:

$$L = 5m \frac{dx}{dt} \frac{dx}{dt} - .5 c(t) xx \quad ((6)) \text{ where } c(t) = da_1/dt - a_2(t) \quad ((6))$$

To do this: $a_1(t)x \frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} [.5a_1 xx] - .5 \frac{da_1}{dt} xx$. The term $\frac{d}{dt} [.5a_1 xx]$ is not included in the Lagrangian because it contributes nothing to the equations of motion.

((6)) has the form of an oscillator Lagrangian with a time-dependent spring constant.

The Green's function is written as:

$$G(t, t_0) = 0 \text{ for } t < t_0 \text{ and } af(t) + bg(t) \text{ for } t > t_0 \quad ((7))$$

where f(t) and g(t) are solutions of Newton's second law. Note: In the case of a constant spring constant, one might choose x=0 at t₀=0 and then only one solution, say f(t)=sin(ωt) is needed.

Considerable algebra is performed and the final result is given in (2) as:

$$K(x,t, x_0,0) = \sqrt{m / (2 \cdot 3.14 \cdot i R)} \exp\{-i / (2m) [dR(t)/dt \cdot x + V(t)x_0 + Z(t) \cdot x_0] \} \quad ((8))$$

$$\text{With : } R(t) = \{ f(t)g(0) - f(0)g(t) \} / W(0) \text{ where } W \text{ is the Wronskian} \quad ((9))$$

Here we only focus on $R(t)$. Information about $V(t)$ and $Z(t)$ may be found in (2).

Two interesting features emerge from this result, namely $R(t)$ is linked to $f(t)$ and $g(t)$, classical solutions of Newton's second law and the coefficient of xx is of the form $dR/dt / R$.

Classical Action Approach

A third approach for obtaining the propagator for an oscillator is given in (3). We argue that it may be extended to the general oscillator considered in this note. The approach is to use: $Q(t) \exp(-i \text{Action})$ as the propagator where $\text{Action} = \int_{t_1=0}^T dt L(t)$ and $L(t)$ is the Lagrangian. To calculate the Lagrangian, solutions of Newton's second law are needed, but unlike in method 2, these are integrated over time in computing the action. We see, however, that the non-integrated functions (following from the equation of motion) may be linked to the integrated action coefficient of XX .

As a first step, consider the regular oscillator. Following (3):

$$x(t) = X A(Tf-t)/A(T) + Y A(t-0)/A(T) \quad ((10))$$

where $A(t)$ is a solution of Newton's second law.

One may note that if one were calculating the classical action for the case of $X=0$ at $t=0$, then $x(t) = L \sin(\omega t)$ where L is the amplitude. The action is then:

$$\text{Action} = \int dt \left(\frac{1}{2} m \dot{x}^2 - \frac{1}{2} k x^2 \right) = \frac{1}{2} m \int_0^T \dot{x}^2 dt - \frac{1}{2} k \int_0^T x^2 dt$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} m \int_0^T \omega^2 L^2 \cos^2(\omega t) dt - \frac{1}{2} k \int_0^T L^2 \sin^2(\omega t) dt \quad ((11))$$

Here $A(Tf-t) = \sin[\omega(Tf-t)]$ which is 0 for $Tf=t$ so X is the initial point. Taking d/dt of ((10)) to obtain the velocity, and inserting into the Lagrangian yields:

$$\text{XX part of Action} = \frac{1}{2} m \int_0^T \left[\frac{dA}{dt} \right]^2 dt - \frac{1}{2} k \int_0^T A^2 dt \quad (t_1=0 \text{ to } T)$$

$$\text{XX part of Action} = \frac{1}{2} m \int_0^T \omega^2 L^2 \cos^2(\omega t) dt - \frac{1}{2} k \int_0^T L^2 \sin^2(\omega t) dt = \frac{1}{2} m \omega^2 L^2 \frac{T}{2} - \frac{1}{2} k L^2 \frac{T}{2} \quad ((12))$$

Thus, one has the coefficient XX which is linked to T . As argued in previous notes, the Schrodinger equation considers independent changes to X and T (although the overall changes to a function $f(X,T)$ are restricted to: $i\hbar \frac{d}{dt} f = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dX} \frac{d}{dx} f + V(x)$ (XX part). We argued that this represents a fluctuation equation involving different amplitudes which create the fluctuation.

We note that ((11)) and ((12)) are different. ((11)) is only a function of T , while ((12)) contains both X and T , but X is really a function of T .

The Action approach used above may be applied to the more general potential $-\frac{1}{2} c(t) x^2$ where $c(t)$ incorporates the idea of a $b(t)x^2$ potential together with a $d(t)x \frac{dx}{dt}$ potential.

Here, we wish to link the solution for the coefficient of XX in the propagator i.e. $\exp(-i XX$ part of Action) to the two previous approaches.

As a first step, consider Newton's second law for: $L = \frac{1}{2} m \frac{dx}{dt} \frac{dx}{dt} - \frac{1}{2} c(t)x^2$. Then:

$$m \frac{d}{dt} \frac{dx}{dt} + c(t)x = 0 \quad ((13))$$

The fact that ((13)) includes $c(t)$, the potential, allows one to link it to $\frac{dR}{dt} + b(t) + 2c_1(t)R + 4a RR = 0$ ((4)) from method ((1)). Here $a = \frac{1}{2}m$ and $b(t) + 2c_1(t)R$ may be replaced with $\frac{1}{2}c(t)$, the potential. Thus, one has:

$$\frac{dR}{dt} - \frac{1}{2}c(t) + 4RR = 0$$

$$\text{Linking with ((13)) yields: } \frac{dR}{dt} + (.5) 4RR = -\frac{1}{2}m \left[\frac{d}{dt} \frac{dx}{dt} \right] / x \quad ((14)) \quad \text{Let } m=1$$

This suggests that:

$$R = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{dx}{dt} \right) / x. \quad ((15))$$

Thus, we recover the form of section 2 for $R(t)$ and also link it directly to a solution to Newton's second law.

Thus, for the coefficient of XX in the exponent of the propagator, all three methods are linked if one uses a potential $\frac{1}{2}c(t)x^2$ with the potential piece $g(t)x \frac{dx}{dt}$ incorporated into $c(t)$.

If the potential is left as $c_1(t)x^2 + c_2(t)x \frac{dx}{dt}$, then the link is not so straightforward as is seen in a later section.

Example

As an example, one may consider the Schrodinger equation:

$$i\hbar dW/dt = -\hbar^2/2m d^2W/dx^2 + \sin(t)\cos(t)xx - i2\sin(t)\cos(t)x dW/dx \quad ((17))$$

$$c_1 = 2\sin(t)\cos(t)$$

As one can see, ((17)) does not rewrite the potential as $f(t)xx$ and drop a pure $d/dt g(t)$ term as done in method 2.

$$\text{Method 1 (1) yields a solution for } R(t) = \frac{1}{4} \frac{1}{a} \frac{dA/dt}{A} \quad ((18))$$

$$\text{Where } a = \hbar^2/2m \quad (m=1) \text{ and } u = \cos(t)\sinh(t) + \sin(t)\cosh(t) \quad ((19))$$

Thus, method 1 yields R of the form $dA/dt / A$, but this is not directly linked to the solution of Newton's second law. To see if $u=A$ is a solution, one needs to see if it satisfies:

$$d/dt (dA/dt - \sin(t)\cos(t) A) + \sin(t)\sin(t) A + \sin(t)\cos(t) dA/dt = 0 \quad ((20))$$

U is not a solution, but this is no surprise, because ((15)) does not hold as the xd/dx part of the potential exists. For this new case:

$$dR/dt + 2c_1R + 4aRR = -b(t) = d/dt dA/dt - dc_1/dt A \quad ((21))$$

This makes the Action approach a little confusing as one may remove pure $d/dt \{xg(t)\}$ terms from a potential in a Lagrangian because they do not affect the equation of motion and thus obtain a new potential i.e. $.5c(t)xx$ as done in method 2. This means the Schrodinger equation ((17)) would need its potential changed. The resulting propagator with the unchanged potential, however, seems to be different than one with a general $.5c(t)xx$ as one may see that $u(T)$ ((19)) is not a solution of ((20)). Equation ((21)) nevertheless shows that R and A , dA/dt are linked.

We argue that if one used the Schrodinger equation:

$$i\hbar dW/dt = -\hbar^2/2m d^2W/dx^2 + [\sin(t)\cos(t) + \cos(2t)]xx \quad ((22))$$

Then method (1) and the Lagrangian would both give $.5/m dA/dt / A$ as the coefficient of XX .

Case of a Time-Dependent Mass

In the case of a time-dependent mass, method 2 no longer holds because it is explicitly derived for a constant mass. Methods 1 and 3 (the classical Action), however, still hold.

For the classical action approach, Newton's second law now yields:

$$d/dt [m(t) dA/dt] = -c(t) A \quad \text{where } .5c(t)AA \text{ is the potential.}$$

From method 1:

$$dR/dt + .5/m(t) 4RR + .5c(t) = 0$$

Thus, one may combine the two:

$$dR/dt + .5/m(t) 4 RR = d/dt \{ .5 m(t) dA/dt \} / A$$

One may see that $.5 m(t) dA/dt / A$ yields part of the solution, thus one needs:

$$R = m(t) dA/dt / A + B(t) \quad \text{where:}$$

$$dB/dt + 2/m(t) [BB + B m(t) dA/dt / A] = .5 dm/dt dA/dt / A$$

The idea of two terms with one of the form $dA/dt / A$ seems to generally match solutions given in (1).

Conclusion

The Green's function approach of (2) and the classical action $\exp(-i\text{Action})$ of (3) for finding a propagator match a pure time dependent Schrodinger equation approach (1) if $m=\text{mass}=\text{constant}$ and the quadratic potential is of the form $.5c(t)xx$. In (2), it is shown that a potential term $a_1(t)x dx/dt$ may be rewritten as a $b(t)xx$ term and a $d/dt (xx g(t))$ term. The latter does not contribute to the Lagrangian equations of motion and so may be dropped. This means that $b_1(t)xx + b_2(t) x dx/dt$ potential may be always rewritten as $.5c(t)xx$ potential in methods (2) and (3). Method (1), however, starts with a pure potential and so does not modify it in any way. We find that although approaches (1),(2) and (3) agree for a given potential of $.5c(t)xx$ and no $x dx/dt$ potential, for (1) with a $b_1(t)x dx/dt$ potential, different results are obtained, at least for the XX coefficient $\exp(i (XXg_1(t) + YYg_2(t) + XYg_3(t)))$. Methods (1) and (3) may still agree with the two potential pieces, but the link between the coefficient of XX in the propagate and $dA/dt / A$ where A is a solution of Newton's equation are more complicated.

In this note, we show how $g_1(t)$, the coefficient of XX in the Schrodinger equation approach is linked to $dA/dt / A$, where A is a solution of Newton's second law, in approach (3) (which agrees with approach (2)) for the case of a potential $.5c(t)xx$.

References

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